
SOFT SKILLS FOR LIBRARY PROFESSIONALS

Vandana Govind Kelkar

Librarian, Yashwantrao Chavan Mahavidyalaya Halkani, Tal: Chandgad, Dist: Kolhapur.

Corresponding Author - Vandana Govind Kelkar

Email- Sukhhergad68@gmail.com

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7180032

Abstract:

Field of library science is changing very fast because of great impact on information technology. Job of library professionals is blended with IT professionals. To cop up with this new change librarians has to adopt soft skills with educational qualifications. Various soft skills required for library professionals are discussed in this paper.

Key Words: *Library Professionals, Soft Skills, Communication Skills.*

Introduction:

Contribution of science and technology has brought tremendous change in the concept of traditional change. Nowadays, the role of libraries and librarians has changed from storehouse to learning center and information manager. In the present era users needs are also changing. Library professionals' job is also changing. New type of information channels has come like eBooks, blogs, information gateways. Encyclopedias, dictionaries directories are available in electronic form and electronic versions. Libraires are automated and collections are digitized. In this changing environment library and information science professionals require diverse skills, new ideas.

In the present electronic information age, where information is treated as as economic resource and as a social wealth. The present day library professionals required different type of soft skills to provide fight information to right user at right time.

Definition:

Soft skills: Personal qualities that enable you to communicate well with other people. (Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary) The formal usage of this term was done in 1972.

Soft skills are playing a vital role in customer-oriented services. Hard skills cover subject knowledge but soft skills include communication skills, management skill, listen skill etc. Soft skills with qualification results into smooth management.

What are soft skills for library Professionals?

Libraries are now information centers. A Skilled librarian can handle any task successfully. To deal with different types of users according to their demand, with hard skills, soft skills are also essential to flourish library profession. Following are the soft skills useful for library professionals.

Leadership Skill: Librarian should have good leadership quality. Library work and services are not individual work, it is

rather team work. So good leadership quality can be helpful to create skill and confidence among library staff.

Communication Skill: A Good communication skill include knowledge about mother tongue and good command over English language, This knowledge is helpful to write the reports and communicate with students, principal and authorities.

Listening Skill: Users of the library are in different age groups. Their requirements vary. Librarians have to listen with patience every reader and user of the library. Listening is also a way of effective way of communication. It helps in betterment of library services.

Technical Skill: -Technical Skills are those skills which are very much useful to handle technical tools skillfully. Skill of computer operation, barcode technology, creation of database, building and maintaining of digital library.

Librarian should help users providing ready reference service, bibliographic services, and selective dissemination of information services. Library professionals should have the knowledge of computer network, e books, copyright, Internet resources, scanning and downloading software, handling mobile apps for educational purpose.

Traditional/ Basic Skill: Traditional skill include running and operating a general traditional library. Skill of classification cataloguing of documents. With the help of this librarian can manage information in proper way.

Managerial Skill: Librarians are the managers of libraries and information centers. They should have basic skills for managing the different sections. Time Management skill is important skill for a librarian. Though it is difficult to apply total quality management in the library but

librarian should study about if for managerial skill.

Teaching Skill: Librarian is a teacher of teacher regarding information retrieval He/she have to conduct orientation program me for users for optimum utilization of resources available in the library. With teaching skills he should inculcate reading habits among users.

Ready to Learn New Things: Due to advancement of in technology librarian should use latest technology and library professional must able to embrace change In order to cope up with the change, library professional must be able to learn new things related to enhance technology oriented service.

Following steps should be adopted for skill enhancement of library professional in a right track

- i) Skill based curriculum should be provided in library science school.
- ii) Short term courses should be arranged not only for the librarian but also for staff
- iii) Different seminar and workshop, conference etc. should be arranged by professional organization.
- iv) Library profession should interact with those who are working with those who are working with developing digital borderless librarian.

Conclusion:

Librarian and librarians have great role in dissemination of information to the user in Information technology era. Librarian ship is facing new challenge to manage the citation. Soft skill are playing a vital Role in LIS field Systematic blending of hard skill with soft skills always accelerate the profession in right direction.

Reference:

1. Gaikwad, M. N. Use Of Social Networking Sites Among Undergraduate Students Of Arts And Commerce College, Madha, Dist. Solapur, Maharastra.
2. https://ijrssi.in/upload_papers/05032014013627Dr.%20Gabhane%20Sir%20Page%20setup%20for%20IJRSSIS.pdf
3. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=en&user=hYAbHG8AAAAJ&citation_for_view=hYAbHG8AAAAJ:hqOjcs7Dif8C
4. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Mahesh-Gaikwad-4/publication/352101595_Journal_of_Advancements_in_Library_Sciences_Designing_Dynamic_Library_Website_by_Using_Wordpress_Open_Source_Content_Management_System_A_Study/links/60b8f0cd299bf10dff915575/Journal-of-Advancements-in-Library-Sciences-Designing-Dynamic-Library-Website-by-Using-Wordpress-Open-Source-Content-Management-System-A-Study.pdf
5. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/286134788_COMPETENCIES_AND_SOFT_SKILLS_FOR_LIBRARY_PROFESSIONALS_IN_INFORMATION_ERA_PARMESH
6. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330958284_ESSENTIAL_SKILLS_FOR_LIBRARY_PROFESSIONALS
7. RAWATANI M.R.and YUSUF, Mohammad. ” Professional manpower needs for libraries with special reference to skills” ILA Bulletin. Vol.38(3),2002.